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**11TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
SIMULATION AND MODELLING
IN THE
FOOD AND BIO-INDUSTRY
2020**

FOODSIM'2020

**EDITED BY
Jan F.M. Van Impe
and
Monika E. Polańska**

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in the
Food and Bio-Industry
GHENT, BELGIUM**

SEPTEMBER 6-10, 2020

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FOODSIM 2020

PREFACE

Dear Colleagues-Friends,

Welcome in Gent, either virtually or on-site, on KU Leuven's local Technology Campus, to attend the FOODSIM'2020 conference! Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, this year's event has been a bit of a challenge to organize, but we are happy, that we have been able to rise to that challenge and are able to present an interesting scientific programme in print and online, be it at a later than originally published date.

As a result of the large number of submitted papers, we were able to put together an extensive programme covering a large number of topics in two volumes. The first volume you are reading now covers *state-of-the-art research* in modeling and simulation for the food industry while volume two covers *work in progress* and is designated as the Flash Presentations Volume.

This year, FOODSIM is running in parallel with another EUROSIS event on our campus, called SCIFI-IT'2020, (The 4th Science Fiction Prototyping Conference) looking at near future research in different fields including nutrition. The organizers of both events expect significant synergies. FOODSIM'2020 participants can easily attend lectures or even full sessions from the parallel event, including Workshops Sessions. As to FOODSIM'2020 itself, participants are treated to 3 FOODSIM Keynote Lectures and 58 scientific presentations of which 48 are also available as a video presentation (https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLo9oj-L36_Xq3iwXM_MT8eeQPKHF2JOD2).

Fully embedded within the FOODSIM'2020 programme are the numerous presentations provided by members of the EU-COST CA15118 FoodMC Action (*Mathematical and Computer Science Methods for Food Science and Industry*) at the occasion of their Final Meeting, and by ESRs of the H2020-MSCA-ITN-2018-813329 PROTECT European Training Network on *PRedictive mOdelling Tools to evaluate the Effects of Climate change on food safeTy*.

Last but not least, both events share the Social Programme, with a conference dinner at the Foyer of the Gent Theatre House to conclude the conference in (safe) style.

The FOODSIM programme has all ingredients needed to provide you with a rewarding experience at the interface of science and "savoir vivre". The organizers look forward to lively discussions and hope to provide you with a forum for networking and intensified collaboration. Many thanks to all involved in the organization and in the reviewing process!

Jan F.M. VAN IMPE, IPC Chair & Monika E. POLAŃSKA, OC Chair &
KU Leuven/BioTeC+ Research Division

Preface IX
Scientific Programme 1
Author Index 281

CLIMATE CHANGE

The Influence of Climate Change

Can Food Consumption Studies help In Modelling Climate Change?
 Ilija Djekic and Igor Tomasevic7

**Modeling Future Scenarios within the Life Cycle Assessment Framework
 under Climate Change Conditions: Dairy Sector as a Study Case**
 Paola Guzmán, Miguel Mauricio-Iglesias, Almudena Hospido
 and Anna Flysjö11

Considerations in Modelling Energy Demand In the Dairy Supply Chain
 Maria Ioanna Malliaroudaki, Rebecca Ferrari, Rachel Luise Gomes
 and Serafim Bakalis14

Climate Change and Microbial Dynamics

**Multi-scale Modelling Approaches for Microbial Dynamics In the Context
 of Climate Change: a Needs Analysis**
 Lydia Katsini, Simen Akkermans, Satyajeet Bhonsale, Styliani Roufou,
 Sholeem Griffin, Vasilis Valdramidis and Jan F.M. Van Impe 19

**Moisture Sorption Isotherms of Coriander Leaves and Estimation of Shelf
 Life of Dried Coriander Leaves (*Coriandrum Sativum*)**
 Rose D.N. Tchoukouang, Angel A. M. Borges and Margarida C. Vieira22

**A Preliminary Study on the Effect of Temperature and Delayed Packaging
 on The Shelf Life of late Crop Greek Peaches and Nectarines**
 Efstathia Tsakali, Melina Aroni, Mavra Marouda, Anastasia Kanellou,
 John Tsaknis, Dimitra Houhoula, Spiridon Konteles and Dimitrios Timpis29

INNOVATIVE FOOD PRODUCTION AND PROCESSING TECHNOLOGIES

Innovative Food Production and Processing Technologies - Liquids

**Temperature Evolution Inside Liquid Foods of Different Viscosity during
 Reciprocal Agitated Processing In the Shaka Retort**
 Davy Verheyen, Ozan Altin, Fabrizio Sarghini, Dagbjørn Skjånes,
 Torstein Skåra, Jan F. Van Impe and Ferruh Erdogdu.....39

CONTENTS

Microwave Pasteurization of Beer: A Computational Study with Experimental Validation
Ozan Karatas, Huseyin Topcam, Ozan Altin and Ferruh Erdogdu.....43

***In Vitro* Fermentation Kinetics of an Antarctic Yeast and Suitability for Beer Production**
Juan Manuel Cevallos-Cevallos, Christian Guarco and Andrea Morales.....49

Cold Plasma Treatment as a Processing Technology to modify Peanut Oil
Ximena V Yepez, Haci Baykara, Sarah Cady and Kevin M. Keener.....54

Innovative Food Production and Processing Technologies - Solids

Stress Concentration In a Dough Gas Cell Wall
Kossigan B. Dedey, Tiphaine Lucas and David Grenier59

Fast Growth of Eyes In Semi-Hard Cheese: Optimization of a Two-Steps Process using Numerical Simulations
Antoine Lejeune, David Grenier, Yves Diascorn, Christoph Doursat, Denis Flick and Tiphaine Lucas.....65

Effect of High-Frequency Atmospheric Plasma on the Growth of Mung Bean Sprouts
Dmytro S. Kozak, Estefanía García Rodríguez, Renald Blundell, Vladimir S Tsepelev, Simen Akkermans, Jan F.M. Van Impe, Vasilis Valdramidis and Ruben Gatt.....73

Innovative Food Production and Processing Technologies – Drying Techniques

Temperature Uniformity during Microwave Thawing: A Computational Study for Geometry and Rotation Effects
Ozan Altin, Huseyin Topcam, Ozan Karatas, Rancesco Marra and Ferruh Erdogdu.....79

Data Acquisition for Modeling Convective Drying of Yacón (*Smallanthus sonchifolius*) Slices
Bianca Cristine Marques, Artemio Plana-Fattori and Carmen Cecilia Tadini86

COST-FOODMC: MATHEMATICAL AND COMPUTER SCIENCE METHODS FOR FOOD SCIENCE AND INDUSTRY

COST-FoodMC: Environmental Modelling and Pest Control

Environmental Modelling in the Food Supply Chain - Future Perspectives
Ilija Djekic, Jan F.M. Van Impe and Alberto Tonda99

Durable Pasta Packaging with Bio-Based Barrier to prevent Insect Infestation

Urška Vrabec Brodnjak, Jon Jordan and Pasquale Trematerra102

COST-FoodMC: Food Production and Business Analysis

Modelling Food Business in the Context of Agriculture 4.0

Eugen Pop, Alexandrina Sirbu, Mihnea Alexandru Moiescu, Simona Iuliana Caramihai, Ioan Stefan Sacala and Ioan Dumitrache.....109

A Study on Reverse Logistics within Agri-Food Supply Chains

Maria Varadinov and João L. de Miranda112

Computational Complexity Studies on the Robust Design and Scheduling of Chemical Batch Processes

João L. de Miranda116

COST-FoodMC: Food Production Optimization

Hyperspectral Data Analysis for Mould Detection in Cheeselets

Jessica Farrugia, Sholeem Griffin, Vasilis Valdramidis, Kenneth Camilleri and Owen Falzon.....123

FOOD SAFETY

Food Safety - Microbial Detection

Viable but Non-Culturable *Salmonella Enterica Ser. Typhimurium* in Foods in Simulated Gastric and Enteric Fluid by Flow Cytometry

Anthimia Batrinou, Efstathia Tsakali, Dimitra Houhoula, Dimitrios Timpis Jan Van Impe and Spiridon Konteles.....131

Detection of *Brucella* spp. in Milk and Blood Samples of Ruminants Animals by PCR

Ioannis Dimou, Ekaterini Samioti, Dimitrios Vourvidis, Anna Kyrma, Dionisis Antonopoulos, Anthimia Batrinou, Spiridon Konteles, Valentini Stefanou, Spiridon Papatheodorou, Jan Van Impe, Efstathia Tsakali and Dimitra Houhoula136

Food Safety - Environmental Risk Assessment Impact

A Quantitative Risk Assessment of *E. coli* O157:H7 on Ready to Eat Foods following the Application of Biomaterials on Land

Rajat Nag, Bryan K Markey, Paul Whyte, Vincent O'Flaherty, Declan Bolton, Owen Fenton, Karl G. Richards and Enda Cummins141

CONTENTS

Microbial Deterioration of Lamb Meat of Portuguese Origin as affected by Its Intrinsic Properties

Vasco A. P. Cadavez, Ursula Gonzales-Barron, Diogo Félix-Oliveira, Sara Coelho-Fernandes, Gisela Santos-Rodrigues, José M. Lorenzo and Roberto Bermúdez Piedra.....145

Meta-Regression Models describing The Effects of Added Lactic Acid Bacteria on Pathogen Inactivation in Milk and Cheese

Beatriz Nunes Silva, José António Teixeira, Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez.....151

Computational Heat Transfer during Horizontal Rotation Process of Particulate Canned Foods

Ferruh Erdogdu, Angela De Vivo and Fabrizio Sarghini159

Study on the Impact of LED Light on Pseudomonas Fluorescens and Staphylococcus Epidermidis Biofilms

Valeria Angarano, Cindy Smet, Simen Akkermans, Charlotte Watt, André Chieffi and Jan F.M. Van Impe.....164

MULTI-SCALE MODELLING APPROACHES

Computational Simulation of Steak Pan Cooking

Jara M^a Moya, José Ángel Bernad and Silvia Lorente-Bailo175

Transient DEM Simulation of Starch Granule Suspension undergoing Thermal Treatment

Arnesh Palanisamy, Artemio Plana-Fattori, Paul Menut, Marco Ramaioli and Denis Flick178

Towards Agent-Based Modelling of Crop Irrigation

Jorge Lopez-Jimenez, Laurent Dewasme, Nicanor Quijano and A. Vande Wouwer185

Regulation of Aggression in Bacterial Warfare

Ihab Hashem, Viviane De Buck, Mihaela Sbarciog and Jan Van Impe190

SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS

Regression Analysis of Grain Production Transformation In Western, Central and Steppe Regions of the Ukraine

Viktor Zhukovskyy, Larysa Bachyshyna, Nataliya Zhukovska and Yelyzaveta Mykhailova.....197

A Generic Software to support Collective Decision In Food Chains and In Multi-Stakeholder Situations
 Rallou Thomopoulos, Julien Cufi and Maxime Le Breton201

Data Driven Modelling of the Beer Aging. Formation and Release of Beer Staling Aldehydes
 Carlos Andre Muñoz, Paula Bustillo Trueba, Barbara Jaskula-Goiris
 Luc de Cooman and Jan Van Impe.....208

Silage Production from the Residues of Plantain (*Musa AAB* Simmonds): A Nutritional Analysis through Process Simulation
 James A. Gómez, Oscar J. Sánchez, José A. Teixeira and Clarisse Nobre.....216

FOOD PSE – FOOD PROCESS SYSTEMS ENGINEERING

Food PSE - Food Process Systems Engineering Methodology

Cultivation and Monitoring of a Gut Microbiota Model System
 Theodora Akritidou, Cindy Smet, Simen Akkermans and Jan F.M. Van Impe ..225

Upgrading the Mating Step In Genetic Multi-Objective Optimisation Algorithms using Sexual Selection
 Viviane De Buck, Ihab Hashem, Mihaela Sbarciog and Jan Van Impe233

Studying the Growth and Substrate Consumption of *Pichia Pastoris* for the Bio-production of Recombinant Sweet-Proteins
 Jewel Ann Joseph, Simen Akkermans and Jan F.M. Van Impe.....238

Food PSE - Solids

Modelling Convective Drying of Food Products under Large Deformation
 Bianca Cristine Marques, Artemio Plana-Fattori, Carmen Cecilia Tadini, and Denis Flick247

Modelling of the Rehydration Process of Dried Broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *italica*) Stems
 Irem Erdem and Cristina L.M. Silva255

Food PSE - Liquids

3D Simulation of Oxidation Reactions in Deep Fryer: Interactions with Anisothermal Oil Flow and Design
 Maxime Touffet, Paul Smith, Joël Wallecan and Olivier Vitrac.....263

Observer-Based Predictive Control of a Continuous Co-Fermentation Process for Ethanol Production
 Mihaela Sbarciog, Satyajeet Bhonsale and Jan Van Impe268

CONTENTS

Multi-Objective Optimal Control of Beer Fermentation Process using Pomodoro Satyajeet Bhonsale, Mihaela Sbarciog, Jan Van Impe	273
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MOISTURE SORPTION ISOTHERMS OF CORIANDER LEAVES AND ESTIMATION OF SHELF LIFE OF DRIED CORIANDER LEAVES (*Coriandrum Sativum*)

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KEYWORDS

Coriander, Shelf life, Sorption isotherm, estimation, model testing.

ABSTRACT

Coriander is an annual herbaceous plant belonging to the family *Umbellifereae* (*Aplaceae*). The green, young coriander leaves (cilantro) are commonly used in Mediterranean culinary as garnishes and spices but have a short shelf life. Dried coriander can be an alternative, but its shelf life within different environments and package materials has to be determined. The objective of this study was to determine the shelf life of dried coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*) leaves, packed in polyethylene (PE) and polyamide-ethylene vinyl alcohol-polyethylene (PA-EVOH-PE) pouches with 30 μ thickness. The water vapor permeability coefficient was first estimated for both PE pouches (54.5 $\pm$ 14.9g. μ m/day/m²/kPa) and PA-EVOH-PE pouches (39.1 $\pm$ 5.5g. μ m/day/m²/kPa). The Moisture Sorption Isotherms of fresh and dried coriander leaves were next determined at 23°C, over a range of relative humidity values (11 to 81 %). In an attempt to find the best model to fit the experimental data six sorption models were tried, being the best fit obtained with the Caurie model ($R^2 = 0.999$) with model parameters ($a_{dried} = -3.58 \pm 0.04$, $b_{dried} = 3.50 \pm 0.06$) for dried leaves and the Halsey model ($R^2 = 0.993$) for fresh leaves with model parameters ($a_{fresh} = 0.81 \pm 0.05$, $b_{fresh} = 0.70 \pm 0.06$). The estimated shelf life was longer for dried coriander leaves packed in PA-EVOH-PE pouches (34 days) than when packed in PE pouches (24 days) at 70% storage humidity for a critical moisture of 22.7%.

INTRODUCTION

Coriander is an annual herbaceous plant belonging to the family *Umbellifereae* (*Aplaceae*), of which all the parts are

edible. The green, young coriander leaves (cilantro) and the aromatic coriander fruit or seeds find culinary uses as garnishes and spices respectively (D'souza and Lobo 2017). Fresh coriander leaves are very rich in vitamin C 135mg/100g (Kamali et al. 2019). The various parts of this plant such as seeds, leaves, flowers, fruits are known to possess antioxidant, anticonvulsant, antidiabetic, antimutagenic, antimicrobial, antifungal, antibacterial, sedative-hypnotic, diuretic, stomachic, spasmodic and carminative activities. Coriander contains essential oils, limpene, coriandrin, geraniol, citronellol, α -pinene, flavonoids, catechin, gallic acid, vicenin, linalool, etc., which give it the above-assigned properties. Literature also suggests that coriander has been explored in-vivo for its various biological activities such as prevention of oxidative damage, inhibition of microbial growth, diabetes management, neurological disease benefits, pain reduction, etc (D'souza and Lobo 2017).

Characterization of EMC (equivalent moisture content) is very important for predicting the stability and shelf life of agricultural products (Heras et al. 2014). Monitoring water activity provides an understanding of the water present in food which can act as pure water (Ortman 2013), while moisture content provides the details of how much total water is in the food. Water activity is an important parameter in controlling water migration and is a tool that can be used to ensure product safety while maximizing shelf life. This can be used to help control quality attributes such as texture, flavor, appearance as well as characterize physical, chemical and microbial stability. Water activity which participates in the degradation reactions in biosystems depends both on water content and the properties of the diffusion surface (Heras et al. 2014).

The food sorption isotherm describes the thermodynamic relationship between water activity and the equilibrium of the moisture content of a food product at constant temperature and pressure. The knowledge and understanding

of sorption isotherms are highly important in food science and technology for the design and optimization of drying equipment, design of packages, predictions of quality, stability, shelf-life, calculating moisture changes that may occur during storage (Andrade et al. 2011) and for the determination of critical moisture and water activity for acceptability of products that deteriorate mainly by moisture gain (Togrul and Arslan 2007). The sorption isotherms are commonly presented by mathematical models based on empirical and/or theoretical criteria. A large number of isotherm models are available which can be categorized into various groups; kinetic models based on an absorbed monolayer of water (BET model), kinetic models based on a multilayer and condensed film (GAB model), semi-empirical (Halsey model) and purely empirical models (e.g. Oswin and Smith models). The moisture sorption isotherms are unique for every material and must be evaluated experimentally (Muzaffar and Kumar 2016).

Changes in water activity by absorption of water when a product is exposed to a high humidity environment or when exposed to a low humidity environment give rise to undesirable or desirable changes in shelf life. These changes can be physical, chemical or microbiological. Understanding and maintaining the critical water activity level of a food product through suitable packaging will extend shelf life. This is due to the inherent biological nature of products, spoilage or deterioration cannot be completely inhibited, although the shelf life can be increased by adopting different packaging materials and various storage conditions (Singh and Anderson 2004). The objective of this experiment was to obtain experimental data to develop moisture sorption isotherms for dried and fresh coriander leaves and to estimate the shelf life of dried coriander leaves in different packaging materials.

METHODOLOGY

Determination of equilibrium Moisture content (EMC)

Saturated solutions at different relative humidity levels (shown in Table 1) were prepared by adding the salts to water in desiccators. Each sample of coriander leaves in Petri dishes was stored in a desiccator with a different relative humidity (RH) level. The weight of the samples was measured every week until equilibrium between the samples and the environment was reached. Equilibrium is reached when negligible changes in the weight of the samples are observed. Once equilibrium was reached, the weights (W_e) of the samples were recorded and the water activity (a_w) was measured for all the samples using a hygrolab water activity meter. The process was repeated for dried and fresh coriander leaves. The equilibrium moisture content was expressed on a dry weight basis (g of water / g dry matter); EMC was determined at a room temperature of

approximately 23°C. A plot of EMC versus a_w was plotted to represent the moisture sorption isotherms of fresh and dried coriander.

Table 1: Saturated salt solutions and relative humidity levels

Salts	RH %
Lithium Chloride	11
Magnesium Chloride	33
Potassium Carbonate	45
Sodium Nitrite	65
Ammonium Sulphate	81

Determination of water vapor permeability coefficient (WVP) and Water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) of plastic material

Two plastic pouches made of different films were used: 1) Polyethylene (PE) and 2) Polyamide-Ethylene Vinyl Alcohol-Polyethylene (PA-EVOH-PE) were fabricated using a heat sealer. The length and width of each pouch were measured using a 30 cm ruler. The thickness of each pouch was measured. Each pouch was filled with 20 g of the desiccant (silica) previously weighed using an analytical balance and the weights of the pouches containing silica were measured. The pouches were stored in desiccators and weighed every day. This assay was performed at room temperature (23°C) and at 100% relative humidity. The assay was performed in triplicate for each plastic material.

Determination of initial moisture content (M_i)

Approximately 1.5 to 2g of coriander leaves were placed in metal plates and transferred to an oven at 105°C to dry. The weight of the dried (W_d) sample was measured and recorded using an analytical balance. This assay was performed in duplicate. The initial moisture content, evaporated water (water loss), and dry matter were calculated with the data obtained. This process was performed for fresh and dried coriander leaves.

DATA ANALYSIS

Moisture Sorption Isotherm models of dried coriander

The EMC of dried and fresh coriander versus a_w were fitted to six mathematical models (Table 2) using Stata software to determine equation coefficients (a and b) with the aim to mathematically express the relation between the water

activity of food and its moisture content. A model was considered the best fit based on the highest R^2 value obtained, the R^2 values close to 1 indicate the highest goodness of fit to the model. The best MSI model was the Caurie model (equation 1) with an R^2 value of 0.999 for dried coriander and Halsey model (equation 8) for the fresh coriander with an R^2 value of $R^2= 0.993$, the models' data were represented with the experimental data in a plot of EMC vs a_w using the predicted EMC values obtained using equation (1) and equation (2).

Table 2: Moisture sorption isotherm models for Coriander

Model	Estimated Parameters		
		Fresh	Dried
Caurie $EMC = \exp(a + b \cdot a_w)$ (1)	a	-2.11±0.30	-3.58±0.04
	B	4.68±0.47	3.50±0.06
	R^2	0.994	0.999
	R^2_{adj}	0.989	0.999
	RMSE	0.188	0.004
Halsey $EMC = \left(\frac{-a}{\ln a_w}\right)^{1/b}$ (2)	A	0.81±0.05	0.70±0.07
	B	0.70±0.06	1.28±0.17
	R^2	0.996	0.991
	R^2_{adj}	0.993	0.984
	RMSE	0.156	0.028
Henderson $EMC = \left[\frac{\ln(1-a_w)}{a}\right]^b$ (3)	a	-1.41±0.15	0.81±0.02
	B	0.59±0.06	-1.14±0.03
	R^2	0.993	0.999
	R^2_{adj}	0.989	0.999
	RMSE	0.198	0.004
Iglesias-Chirife $EMC = a + b\left(\frac{a_w}{1-a_w}\right)$ (4)	a	-0.15±0.19	0.04±0.01
	B	1.43±0.14	0.12±0.17
	R^2	0.973	0.995
	R^2_{adj}	0.964	0.993
	RMSE	0.182	0.010
Smith $EMC = a - b(\ln(1-a_w))$ (5)	a	-3.52±	-0.31±0.01
	B	-1.11±	-0.05±0.01
	R^2	0.946	0.996
	R^2_{adj}	0.928	0.995
	RMSE	0.257	0.008
Oswin $EMC = a \left[\frac{a_w}{(1-a_w)}\right]^b$ (6)	a	1.26±0.89	0.16±0.00
	B	1.11±0.10	0.80±0.02
	R^2	0.995	0.999
	R^2_{adj}	0.9914	0.999
	RMSE	0.172	0.006

WVTR and WVP of plastic films

The WVTR was calculated using equation (7).

$$WVTR = \frac{Q}{tA} \quad (7)$$

Where, Q = weight change (g), t = time (day), Q/t = slope of the linear regression of weight change versus time and A = doubled area of the plastic pouch (m^2).

The WVP was calculated after obtaining WVTR, the WVTR was substituted in equation (8)

$$WVP = \frac{WVTR}{p^s} \times l \quad (8)$$

where, p^s = water saturation pressure at 25 °C (3.171 kPa), l = thickness of plastic pouch (μm)

Equilibrium moisture content (M_e) and initial moisture content (M_i)

The equilibrium moisture content on a dry basis was calculated using equation 9;

$$M_e = \frac{W_i - W_{dm}}{W_{dm}} \quad (9)$$

Where, W_i is the initial sample weight in grams and W_{dm} is the corresponding weight of dry matter of the sample. The dry matter was obtained by subtracting the weight of the petri plate from the total Final weight of the sample at equilibrium.

The initial moisture content (M_i) was obtained by dividing the amount of water loss in grams by the dry matter. The water loss was estimated following the assumption that the coriander leaves had lost their entire water content at the equilibrium point. The quantity of water loss was estimated once equilibrium was reached, by subtraction (initial weight - final weight).

Estimation of Shelf Life of dried coriander

Considering that the isotherm portion of interest can be linearized (equation 10),

$$me = a + b \cdot a_w \quad (10)$$

where me = moisture content in g H₂O per g dry matter, a_w = water activity, b = slope of curve, and a = constant.

The moisture content can be substituted for water gain using the relationship:

$$\theta_s = \frac{W_s \cdot L \cdot b}{WVP \cdot A \cdot p_o} \ln \frac{me - m_i}{me - m_c} \quad (11)$$

Where, θ_s = shelf life of a dried product gaining moisture with time (days), L = film thickness (μm), W_s = weight of dry solids (g), WVP = water vapor permeability of plastic films ($g \cdot \mu m \cdot day^{-1} \cdot m^{-2} \cdot kPa^{-1}$), A = Surface area of plastic package (m^2), p_o = vapor pressure of pure water at the storage temperature (not the actual vapor pressure outside

the package) (kPa), b is the slope of the moisture sorption isotherm when treated as a linear function at 95% confidence, m_e = equilibrium moisture content of the food if exposed to the RH outside the package, m_i = initial moisture content (M_i of dried coriander converted to percentage), Y_c = critical moisture content of product.

The shelf life of dried coriander in different plastic packaging (PE and PA-EVOH-PE) was thus estimated using equation (11) above (Robertson 2006). The shelf life was calculated under the following conditions, $W_s = 50$ g, $A = 0.03$ m², $L = 30$ μ m, $p_o = 3.171$ kPa, $b = 0.6306$. The humidity (moisture content) at storage, was set at 70%. The mc value was calculated using the assumption that the product will be undesirable at a_w of 0.6, this a_w and coefficients A and B were substituted in the Caurie equation to obtain the corresponding Me value. The Me value obtained represented the mc , the critical moisture content was found to be 22.7%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Moisture sorption isotherm (MSI) and equilibrium moisture content (EMC)

The initial moisture content (M_i) was calculated by dividing the quantity of evaporated water in grams by the dry matter. The initial moisture content values of fresh coriander and dried coriander are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Initial moisture content (M_i) of coriander leaves

Coriander	M_i g water/ g dry matter
Fresh	14.28±10.14
Dried	0.16±0.01

The fresh samples (placed in desiccators) reached equilibrium through moisture loss, after 4 weeks while the dried samples reached equilibrium through moisture gain, after 5 weeks. Thus, the sorption data were obtained by desorption in the case of fresh coriander and adsorption for dried coriander. Desorption translates to the fact that a product will lose moisture when stored in an environment with a relatively lower RH and adsorption means that the product will gain moisture when stored in an environment with a RH higher compared to the humidity of the product. Water adsorption by food products is a process in which water molecules progressively and reversibly mix with food solids via chemisorption, physical adsorption, and multilayer condensation (Andrade et al. 2011). In contrast, dried coriander at RH of 11% and 33% demonstrated a decrease in the weight of the samples at equilibrium, this means that the samples had a higher humidity compared to

the humidity of the surrounding environment in the desiccator and were losing moisture.

For the fresh and dried products, as the water activity increased, the equilibrium moisture content (EMC) increased at a temperature of 23°C. This is consistent with similar results reported for several products such as leaves of lemon balm (Argyropoulos et al. 2012) and leaves of olives (Nourhène et al. 2008). Rao et al. (2006) reported an increase in the EMC at 5°C and 35°C, from 5.75% and 3.55% at 0.23 a_w to 104.82% and 88.64% at 0.98 a_w , respectively. An experiment conducted by Heras et al. (2014) on the MSI of dried persimmon leaves demonstrated an increase in Me as the temperature increased at a constant water activity. Moreover, the Me of dry persimmon leaves increases as the water activity increased, this is a similar observation to the results of the present study.

The sorption isotherm of dried and fresh coriander presented in Figure 1 demonstrates a desorption curve (fresh coriander) and adsorption curve (dried coriander). Dragicevic and Sredojevic (2011) stated that plant tissues will typically exhibit a sigmoid shape in adsorption and desorption isotherms curves, presumably due to the existence of three types of water-binding sites in tissues; strong (I), weak (II) and multilayer molecular sorption sites (III) and the difference between the two curves shows hysteresis, indicating the irreversibility of water sorption in the tissues during dehydration and rehydration. Equilibrium moisture content was higher for the desorption curve than that of adsorption at a particular water activity (Figure 1). The hysteresis was therefore observed. The curves did not exhibit sigmoidal behaviors typically seen in plant products even though the desorption curve of fresh coriander demonstrated an inflection point which is a characteristic of most isotherms of plant product, which is probably due to the lack of experimental data at lower a_w (0.1 to 0.3) and higher a_w (0.8 to 1.0). In contrast, a sigmoidal shape was observed in the MSI of dry persimmon leaves (Heras et al. 2014).

Two regions could be identified in the adsorption isotherms of dried coriander, one region characterized by slower water uptake and another region characterized by higher water uptake. The slower water uptake region is between a_w of 0.36 to 0.47 and the higher water uptake is observed in the region of a_w at 0.47 to 0.75. Two regions could be identified in the desorption isotherm of fresh coriander, a region of rapid water loss at a_w of 0.57 to 0.70 and a region of slower water loss at a_w of 0.41 to 0.57. Rao et al (2006) identified three regions in the MSI of chhana podu; region I (a_w 0.0–0.35), region II (a_w 0.35–0.85) and region III (a_w 0.85–1.0). The moisture uptake was slow in the region I, followed by a linear and steady rise in the region II and a subsequent accelerated rise in the region III. In the sorption curve, for 5°C and 35°C, the moisture content between 0.85 and 0.97 a_w ranged from 32.11 to 104.82% and 28.43 to 88.64%, respectively.

Figure 1: Adsorption (dry) and desorption (fresh) isotherms of Coriander leaves at 23 °C

Modeling of MSI of dried coriander

Figure 1 shows the model fitted to the MSI of fresh and dried coriander leaves using the values of M_e predicted using the Halsey and Caurie models respectively. Both models were chosen based on the value of R^2_{adj} (close to 1) and to R^2 and on the lower value of the Root MSE. In contrast, it was reported that the models which best represented the behavior of the adsorption curves of the dehydrated leaves and stem of coriander were the Smith and Peleg model (Silva et al. 2010). Caurie model has been used successfully by other researchers (Rao et al. 2006) for the MSI of chhana pod.

Estimation of shelf life of dried coriander in different packaging materials

The shelf life of coriander leaves was found to be 34 days for PA-EVOH-PE film and 24 days for PE film when stored at 70% RH. The PE film had a higher vapor permeability compared to the PA-EVOH-PE film, thus the shelf life increased with decreasing WVP. The water vapor permeability coefficient (WVP) of the film determines how fast or slow the water vapor can permeate through the film. Correspondingly, it affects the shelf life of the product. In the present experiment, the WVP was found to be $39.1 \text{ g}\cdot\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{kPa}^{-1}$ for PA-EVOH-PE film and $54.5 \text{ g}\cdot\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{kPa}^{-1}$ for PE film (Table 4). Xiong (2002) determined a WVTR for LDPE of $1.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$.

Table 4: Experimental Water Vapor Transmission Rates of PE And PA-EVOH-PE Plastic Film

Material	WVTR $\text{g}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$	WVP $\text{g}\cdot\mu\text{m}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{kPa}^{-1}$
PA-EVOH-PE	2.1 ± 0.3	39.1 ± 5.5
PE	5.9 ± 1.6	54.5 ± 14.9

The moisture vapor transmission rate (MVTR), also called the water vapor transmission rate (WVTR), is a measure of how much water vapor mass can penetrate an area of a material in a given time period, is given in units of mass per area per time (Keller and Kouzes 2017). Table 4 shows that the main value of the water vapor transmission rate was found to be $2.1\pm 0.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for PA-EVOH-PE film and $5.9\pm 1.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for PE film. The testing conditions were 25 °C and 100 % RH. These results indicate that the PA-EVOH-PE film has a better water vapor barrier compared to PE film and will, therefore, exhibit better preservation properties for dried products compared to PE films. Christine Samaniego (1989), indicated that the standard equation for mass transfer (equation 12)

$$P=D\cdot S \quad (12)$$

where P = Permeability, D = diffusion coefficient and S = Solubility coefficient, assumes that the water sorption properties for a film are linear. Thus, many films will show a change in WVTR depending on vapor pressure conditions on each side of the film. Samaniego (1989) supported that a linear relationship exists between WVTR and vapor pressure difference for the three plastic films studied, which are the low-density polyethylene (LDPE), Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) and a laminate of both films. The WVTR value for PET film was much higher than the LDPE film, stating that LDPE is a good water vapor barrier, and as expected, the WVTR value of the laminate film was lower than the other films because of the double polyethylene layer in the laminate. A lower vapor transmission rate of plastic films gives a longer shelf life for dried products, this was observed by Yaptenco et al. (2017) in a study to estimate the shelf life of dried sandfish when packed in a $43.6 \mu\text{m}$ thick PE film and $35.6 \mu\text{m}$ oriented polypropylene (OPP) film. The shelf-life was longer for the dried sandfish packaged in OPP film with a lower vapor transmission rate.

CONCLUSION

The results show that the MSI did not exhibit sigmoidal behaviors typically seen in plant products. However, the desorption curve of fresh coriander demonstrated an inflection point which is commonly observed in isotherms of most plant products. The experimental results showed

the phenomenon of hysteresis in the sorption isotherms. The equilibrium moisture content (EMC) of dried and fresh coriander leaves can be predicted using models of sorption isotherms. The Caurie model and Halsey model gave better fit to the experimental data of dried and fresh coriander leaves respectively. It was observed that EMC increased with increasing water activity for both the fresh and dried products. At water activity values higher than 0.4 the water uptake rate and water loss rate increased rapidly for the dried and fresh coriander leaves respectively.

The shelf life of the product decreased with an increase in water vapor permeability of the plastic film and the role of water activity in shelf-life prediction is of great importance particularly in dried food products sensitive to moisture gain or loss which are packaged in materials which are permeable to water vapor. It was demonstrated that the coriander leaves that were packaged in the PA-EVOH-PE film with a WVP of $39,1 \pm 5.5 \text{ g} \cdot \mu\text{m} \cdot \text{day}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{kPa}^{-1}$ would have a longer shelf life (34 days) compared to the coriander leaves packaged in PE film. This is due to the double barrier PA-EVOH-PE packaging that gives a longer shelf life to the product due to the lower vapor permeability of the plastic film. The determination of critical moisture content of coriander leaves of 22.7% is considered crucial in assessing the shelf life of the product as it determines the period at which the products becomes unacceptable or undesirable.

FUTURE RESEARCH

According to the observations made in the current experiment, the isotherms of coriander leaves did not exhibit the sigmoidal behavior at 23 °C. The above shelf life values were estimated theoretically. In the next step of the research, the isotherms of adsorption and desorption will be studied under a wider range of water activities at different temperatures and the acceptability of the samples will be monitored over time when packaged with different polymer materials to verify the estimated values and to refine the above conclusions.

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REFERENCES

- Argyropoulos, D.; Alex, R.; Kohler, R.; and Mueller, J. 2012. "Moisture sorption isotherms and isosteric heat of sorption of leaves and stems of lemon balm (*Melissa officinalis* L.) established by dynamic vapor sorption". *LWT Food Science and Technology*, 47(2), 324-331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2012.01.026>
- D'Souza, R. and Lobo, V. 2017. "Effects of Temperature and Storage Duration on Antioxidant Status in *Coriandrum Sativum*. Linn". *International Journal of Life-Sciences Scientific Research*, 3(3), 1055-1058. <https://doi.org/10.21276/ijlssr.2017.3.3.15>
- Dragicevic, V. and Sredojevic, S. 2011. "Thermodynamics of Seed and Plant Growth", In *Thermodynamics - Systems in Equilibrium and Non-Equilibrium 2011*, J.C. Moreno-Piraján (Ed.). InTech, Rijeka <https://doi.org/10.5772/19726>
- Heras, R.M.L.; Heredia, A.; Castelló, M. L.; and Andrés, A. 2014. "Moisture sorption isotherms and isosteric heat of sorption of dry persimmon leaves". *Food Bioscience*, 7, 88-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2014.06.002>
- Iglesias, H. A. and Chirife, J. 1976. "Prediction of the effect of temperature on water sorption isotherm of food materials". *Journal of Food Technology*, 11(2), 109-116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1976.tb00707.x>
- Kamali, R.; Shoba N.; and Meenakshi, P. 2019. "Studies on Nutritional Composition of Coriander Leaf Powder As Influenced By Different Drying Methods". *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 7(3), 1711-1714.
- Keller, P. E. and Kouzes, R. T. 2017. *Water Vapor Permeation in Plastics*. Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, Washington. <https://doi.org/10.2172/1411940>
- Mathlouthi, M. and Rogé, B. 2003. "Water vapour sorption isotherms and the caking of food powders". *Food Chemistry*, 82(1), 61-71. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0308-8146\(02\)00534-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0308-8146(02)00534-4)
- Muzaffar, K. and Kumar, P. 2016. "Moisture sorption isotherms and storage study of spray dried tamarind pulp powder". *Powder Technology*, 291, 322-327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2015.12.046>
- Nourhène, B.; Neila, B.; Mohammed, K.; and Nabil, K. 2008. "Sorption isotherms and isosteric heats of sorption of olive leaves (Chemlali variety): Experimental and mathematical investigations". *Food and Bioprocess Processing*, 86(3), 167-175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbp.2007.10.010>
- Oswin, C. R. 1946. "The kinetics of package life. III. Isotherm". *Journal of the Society of the Chemical Industry*, 65(12), 419-421. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ctth.5000651216>
- Rao, J.K.; Dhas, P.H.A.; Emerald, M.E.F.; Ghosh, B.C.; Balasubramanyam, BV.; and Kulkarni, S. 2006. "Moisture sorption characteristics of chhana podo at 5°C and 35°C". *Journal of Food Engineering*, 76(3), 453-459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2005.04.048>
- Robertson G.L. 2006. *Food Packaging Principles and Practice*, 2nd edn. CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida.
- Silva, A.S.; Almeida, F.A.C.; Alves, N.M.C.; Melo, K.S.; and Gomes, J.P. 2010. "Característica higroscópica e termodinâmica do coentro desidratado". *Revista Ciência Agronômica*, 41(2), 237-244. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1806-66902010000200010>
- Singh, R. and Anderson, B. 2004. "Understanding and Measuring the Shelf-Life of Food", In *Major types of food spoilage: an*